

THE ROLE OF THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY IN INCREASING THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF THE ECONOMY OF UZBEKISTAN

Musayeva Shoirazimovna

Professor of Samarkand Institute of Economic and Service

Ikromova Takhmina

Marketer of the enterprise City of Samarkand

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7149316>

Abstract. This article examines the establishment of the production of finished products in the textile industry, the organization of network management, the distribution of resources and production capacities.

Keywords: economy, textile industry, export, market, product, modernization, diversification.

РОЛЬ ТЕКСТИЛЬНОЙ ПРОМЫШЛЕННОСТИ В ПОВЫШЕНИИ ЭКСПОРТНОГО ПОТЕНЦИАЛА ЭКОНОМИКИ УЗБЕКИСТАНА

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается организация производства готовой продукции в текстильной промышленности, организация сетевого управления, распределение ресурсов и производственных мощностей.

Ключевые слова: экономика, текстильная промышленность, экспорт, рынок, товар, модернизация, диверсификация.

INTRODUCTION

The socially oriented model of Uzbekistan's own market economy is related to the development of foreign economic activity, as well as the determination of the ways of integration into world economic relations, and the perspective of the market economy is related to its international integration.

After the independence of our country, the implementation of structural changes in the economy, the establishment of export-oriented production enterprises and the production of competitive products through technical and technological updating, the acquisition of new territories, and the measures aimed at further increasing the country's export potential were given great importance.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Modernization and diversification of the leading branches of industry, introduction of modern technologies of processing of raw materials and semi-finished products, targeted support of productions highly competitive in the world market, helped to increase the share of processing industry in production.

If in 2015, the share of the processing industry in the total volume of industrial production was 73.8%, by 2021 it will increase to 80.3%.

In the total volume of industrial production, the volume of production of products with high added value increased in the following sectors: food, textiles, chemicals, pharmaceuticals and other sectors.

Only in 2021, compared to the previous year, the increase in the volume of production in the processing industry - 6.4%, including the production of basic pharmaceutical products and preparations - 40.3%, chemical products, rubber and plastic goods - 34.4%, other non-metallic

mineral products - 20.9%, food products, beverages, tobacco products - 10.8%, textile products, clothing, leather products - 9, was 0%.

Table 1.1

Production of industrial products by types of economic activity (in percent)

	2015 year	2021 year	Growth rate in 2021 compared to 2015, in percent
Total	100.0	100.0	156.1
including:			
mining and open pit operations	15.0	9.6	121.0
processing industry	73.8	80.3	166.6
of which:			
textile products, production of clothes and leather products	14.4	16.7	168.8
electricity, gas, steam supply and air conditioning	10.7	9.4	125.2
water supply, sewage system, waste collection and disposal	0.5	0.7	165.9

RESULTS

As can be seen from the table above. light industry, including the textile industry, is gaining an important place in the industrial sectors of our country. At the same time, the importance of textile products in the export structure of our country is increasing. In 2021 in the structure of Uzbekistan's exports, the group of other goods has a certain place with a share of 35.7%, and the volume of textile products included in this group is 1133.2 mln. was USD and increased by 22.8% compared to the same period last year.

The President of our country pays great attention to the development of the textile industry. In the last year, several decrees and decisions on the further development of this industry were announced:

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated December 14, 2017 No. PF-5285 "On measures for the rapid development of the textile and sewing and knitting industry" It is the most important condition to increase the efficiency and profitability of growing and processing cotton raw materials.

Taking this into account, practical measures aimed at ensuring further development of this sector are being consistently implemented in our country. In particular, by the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-2687 dated December 21, 2016, the program of measures for the further development of the textile and sewing-knitting industry in 2017-2019 was approved.

DISCUSSION

Today, a textile network with high production potential has been formed in the republic, where about 7,000 enterprises are operating. Cotton fiber production capacity of 1.4 million tons has been created, of which about 60 percent is used to meet the needs of local textile enterprises.

First of all, the existence of systemic problems related to the establishment of the production of finished products, the organization of network management, the distribution of

resources and production capacities, and the lack of high qualification of personnel lead to the low profitability of the cultivation of raw cotton and its processing, the production and export of finished products. due to the fact that it is not at the levelis coming

Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Measures for the Rapid Development of the Textile and Sewing-Knitting Industry" defines the first complex of measures to solve existing problems, as well as to expand the production of high-quality textile products and promote them to world markets. gave

With this document, the following important directions of further reform of the textile industry were defined, in particular:

- increasing the share of the textile industry in the economy, increasing the volume and quality of textile products produced in the country;
- a fundamental revision of the management system of the textile industry;
- further improvement of the standardization and certification system in the field of textile industry;
- wide introduction of advanced information and communication technologies to the network;
- implementation of the cluster model of textile industry development;
- ensuring the balance of the distribution of raw material resources and the location of the network enterprises being established in the interrelationship with the development of logistics and engineering infrastructure;
- wide implementation of advanced innovation technologies, know-how, design developments in the production process, localization of production of modern samples of fittings and accessories;
- radical improvement of the system of personnel training, retraining and advanced training for the textile industry.

It should be noted that this Decree is an important step in the practical implementation of the concept of administrative reforms in the Republic of Uzbekistan approved by the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5185 dated September 8, 2017, which provides for further reduction of administrative influence on economic sectors and expansion of market mechanisms of management.

In particular, with the Decree, the textile and sewing-knitting industry in the Republic of Uzbekistan, which consists of more than 20 measures to improve the management and personnel training system, modernize the technological process and infrastructure of production, textile industry, activate foreign economic activity, introduce international standards to the textile industry Rapid development "Roadmap" approved.

JSC "Uzbekengilsanoat" is actively attracting investments, ensuring stable growth of production and export volumes. The share of semi-finished textile products in the total volume of export was equal to 14.4%. In 2021, the export volume was 1090 million dollars. In 2015-2021, the volume of export of light industrial products is 660 mln. 1090 million dollars. dollar, or in other words, the export volume increased by 1.6 times.

If we analyze the export structure of the product, we can see that the share of cotton kalava yarn in the total export of light industrial products is decreasing, and the share of yarn yarn and ready-made knitted and crocheted goods is increasing (Table 2).

Export structure of JSC "Uzbekengilsanoat" in 2020-2021

Export of light industrial products, %	Cotton thread	Ready-made knitwear	Threading	Silk products	Other products
2020 year	44.2	16.8	4.4	1.0	10.6
2021 year	35.4	18.7	6.9	3.1	15.9

Until today, local textile enterprises had to buy cotton fiber from the monopoly supplier at export prices - "Uzpakhtasanoatexport" JSC. This procedure reduced the profitability and competitiveness of textile production.

According to the experiment initiated by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, enterprises of the textile industry will finance the main expenses of farms for the cultivation of cotton raw material by giving an advance of at least 60% of the contracted value. In this case, the cotton raw materials supplied to the enterprises are used only for further deep processing and production of ready competitive products.

Today, a textile industry with a huge production potential has been formed in the republic, and nearly 7,000 enterprises are effectively operating in its system. Also, capacities for the production of 1.4 million tons of cotton fiber have been created, and about 60 percent of this raw material is used to meet the needs of textile enterprises of our country. If only 436 organizations were part of JSC "Uzbekengilsanoat" before, now all enterprises and organizations of the textile industry can become members of "Uztoqilikanoat" Association.

This provides a number of advantages for local producers. In particular, enterprises that are members of the "Uztogamichilikanoat" Association are exempted from paying customs fees for imported cotton, artificial and synthetic fibers, wool, raw materials and other materials necessary for the production of textile products that are not produced in the republic (except for fees for processing documents at the customs office). In addition, the Association "Uztogamilikanoat" has been given the right to file a claim in the interests of its members, to file complaints about the decisions of state bodies and other organizations, actions (inaction) of officials during the court process without paying the state duty.

CONCLUSIONS

It should be noted that in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5285 of December 14, 2017, measures are being taken to fundamentally improve the personnel training system. An inventory of existing needs in narrow specialties will be conducted at network enterprises, and a database of authors of the Tashkent Textile and Light Industry Institute and network vocational colleges will be created. In cooperation with this higher education institution, we will supply experts in spinning, knitting, sewing, painting and decoration for the network, as well as prepare experienced technicians working in corporate management enterprises (personnel management, state and public administration). It is planned to organize term (external and evening) courses.

Also, at the event, detailed information on the achievements of the textile and knitting industry in 2017 was presented. The Investment Program of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017 and the Program for further development of the textile and sewing-knitting industry in 2017-2020 were implemented in the program to improve the sector.

In particular, this year, 34 investment projects aimed at modernization of existing enterprises, technical and technological re-equipment and creation of new capacities were

implemented. The total cost of these projects is 356.9 million. is equal to 151.7 million dollars, export potential. made up the dollar.

At the same time, the export indicators of the industry were also discussed at the press conference. 1.16 billion in 2021. it was noted that the dollar product is expected to be exported. Products produced in our country are delivered to more than 50 countries of the world. The share of products with high added value was more than 40 percent. If at the beginning of 2021 there were 293 exporting enterprises in our country, by the end of the year their total number reached 350. Meanwhile, the efforts of 64 trading houses operating in different countries of the world serve to further increase the export performance of the industry.

REFERENCES

1. Message from the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev to the Oliy Majlis. January 24, 2020 - People's Show, January 26, 2020
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 7, 2017 No. PF-4947 "On the Strategy of Actions for the Further Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan".
3. Fundamentals, 5th European Edition. Textbook. - M.: LLC "I.D. Williams", 2013. - 752 p.
4. Soliev A., Vuzrukhnov S. Marketing, market science. Textbook. - T.: Iktisod-Moliya, 2010.-- 424 p.
5. Ergashkhodzhaeva Sh.Yu., Kosimova M.S., Yusupov M.A. Marketing. Textbook. - T.: TDIU, 2011.-- 202 p.
6. Khamraeva S.N. Innovative development of rural infrastructure. Monograph - Tashkent: 2017 - 73 p.
7. Aaker D., et al. Marketing research. Ed. 7th. Per. s angl / Pod red. S. Bozhuk. - SPb.: Peter, 2004, - 848 p.
8. Aksunova G.N. Marketing. - T., 2005.-- 463 p.
9. Bagiev G.L., Tarasevich V.M., Ann X. Marketing: 3rd ed. / Under total. ed. G.L. Bagieva. - SPb.: Peter, 2006, - 736 p.
10. Basovsky L.E. Marketing: Course Lecture. - M.: INFRA-M, 2010.-- 219 p.
11. Boyuk S.G., Kovalik L.N. Marketing research, - St. Petersburg: Peter, 2004. - 461 p.
12. Bronnikova T.S. Marketing: theory, practice: textbook / T.S. Bronnikov - 2nd ed., Revised. and add. - M.: KNORUS, 2010.-- 208 p.
13. Gerasimov B.I., Mozgov N.N. Marketing research of the market: textbook / B.I. Gerasimov, N. Mozgov. - M.: FORUM, 2009.-- 336 p.: Ill.
14. E.P. Golubkov Marketing research: theory, methodology and practice. / 2nd rev. and add. - M.: Finpress, 2003.-- 496 p.
15. E.P. Golubkov Fundamentals of Marketing. 2nd revised and add. - M.: Finpress, 2003.-- 688 p.
16. Grigoriev M.N. Marketing. - M.: Gardariki, 2006, - 366 p.
17. Musaeva Sh.A. Usmonova D.I. Innovative marketing: Study guide. - "TURON PUBLISHING" Samarkand 2021.
18. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F., Sodirovich U. B. Problems in the Implementation of Quality Management Systems in Small Business Enterprises //Eurasian Research Bulletin. – 2022. – T. 7. – C. 54-57.

19. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D. Problems of Marketing in the System of Higher Education //Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability. – 2022. – T. 13. – C. 71-75.
20. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN //EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 1. – C. 1-4.
21. Musayeva S. A., Usmonova D. I., Usmanov F. S. Problems with Marketing Research in the Furniture Market //Eurasian Journal of Academic Research. – 2021.
22. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Development Prospects of Business Subjects in the Republic of Uzbekistan //Web of Scholars: Multidimensional Research Journal. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 4. – C. 13-19.
23. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. The Concept of Marketing Policy in Trade and Service Enterprises //CENTRAL ASIAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATIONS ON TOURISM MANAGEMENT AND FINANCE. – 2022. – T. 3. – №. 8. – C. 1-5.
24. SCIENCE AND INNOVATION INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC JOURNAL VOLUME 1 ISSUE 5 UIF-2022: 8.2 | ISSN: 2181-3337
25. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F. Ways to expand network marketing and e-commerce in the wholesale of medicines //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876. – 2022. – T. 16. – №. 06. – C. 113-116.
26. Azimovna M. S., Abdurozikovich M. Z. Features of the pharmaceutical market of the Republic of Uzbekistan //INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF SOCIAL SCIENCE & INTERDISCIPLINARY RESEARCH ISSN: 2277-3630 Impact factor: 7.429. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 06. – C. 201-206.
27. Azimovna M. S., Shohrukhovich U. S. THE ROLE OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS IN THE FOREIGN TRADE TURNOVER OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMIY JURNALI. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 6. – C. 110-112.
28. Azimovna M. S. IMPROVING THE STUDY OF CONSUMER BEHAVIOR //Gospodarka i Innowacje. – 2022. – C. 109-112.
29. Azimovna M. S. et al. Analysis of the main economic and marketing indicators of FE" DAKA-TEX" LLC //ASIA PACIFIC JOURNAL OF MARKETING & MANAGEMENT REVIEW ISSN: 2319-2836 Impact Factor: 7.603. – 2022. – T. 11. – №. 06. – C. 4-7.
30. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D. Optimal principles of assessing the quality of graduates in higher education //Eurasian Scientific Herald. – 2022. – T. 8. – C. 233-238.
31. Azimovna M. S. THE MAIN DIRECTIONS OF THE MARKETING COMPLEX TO INCREASE THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF PRODUCTS //FORMATION OF PSYCHOLOGY AND PEDAGOGY AS INTERDISCIPLINARY SCIENCES. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. 9. – C. 20-23.
32. Azimovna M. S., Ilkhomovna U. D., Shokhrukhovich U. F. WAYS TO USE MARKETING INFORMATION IN THE PROCESS OF EVALUATING THE ENTERPRISE //World Economics and Finance Bulletin. – 2022. – T. 10. – C. 9-12.

33. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F., Sodirovich U. B. ANALYSIS OF THE MARKET OF TOURIST PRODUCTS OF THE SAMARKAND REGION //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMYIY JURNALI. – 2022. – T. 2. – №. 4. – C. 422-427.
34. Azimovna M. S., Shokhrukhovich U. F., Rofejon o'g'li R. S. THE PROCEDURE FOR ORGANIZING MARKETING RESEARCH AT INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE CONTEXT OF MODERNIZATION IN UZBEKISTAN //BARQARORLIK VA YETAKCHI TADQIQOTLAR ONLAYN ILMYIY JURNALI. – 2022. – C. 392-399.